

Thermodynamic Studies with the Chelating Ion-Exchange Resin-Dowex A-1

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Copper and nickel complexes of Dowex A-1 chelating resin, a polystyrene—DVB matrix with iminodiacetic acid as the functional group, have been prepared by the controlled addition of Cu- and Ni- sulphate to the hydrogen form of the resin at two different temperatures. The equilibrium constants of these reactions have been calculated from the molalities of the ions present. The distribution constants have also been calculated from the amount of the ions present in both the phases. The free energy changes of these reactions have been evaluated by using both the constants, to ascertain the role of water invasion and consequent swelling of the resin. Thermodynamic constants like enthalpy and entropy changes of these reactions have also been calculated by using standard thermodynamic relations. Entropy changes of both the systems are found to be independent of percentage exchange. The enthalpy change of copper-complex is constant but that of Ni- complex decreases as the percentage exchange increases.

The tendency of the formation of metal-chelates with resin—Dowex A-1, their kinetic measurements and equilibrium studies were made by different workers¹⁻¹².

In the present work some of the thermodynamic properties of the chelate formation of this resin with different metal ions were evaluated using the apparent equilibrium constants of the exchange reactions with a view to ascertain the nature of the metal-resin complex and the effect of swelling of the resin on the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resin in the sodium form was obtained from Dow Chemical Co., Midland, Mich¹³. It was pre-treated in the usual way. A sample of this resin in hydrogen form was dried in a vacuum desiccator in presence of fused calcium chloride as desiccant to constant weight at the ambient room temperature. The exchange capacity of this dried sample was determined by the usual method of adding NaOH and NaCl solutions and back titrating the excess alkali¹⁴. The exchange capacity was found to be 478 ± 0.00 meq per gram dry resin.

The equilibrium reaction was carried out between the hydrogen form resin and the chelate forming ions Cu^{++} and Ni^{++} . The resin samples were dried as above and to a known amount of this resin kept in a pyrex bottle provided with ground glass stoppers to prevent evaporation, calculated amount of deionised water and the salt solutions were added in

such a way so that the final volume became 100 ml in each case. pH values were adjusted in every case by adding requisite amount of hydrochloric acid with the help of a Cambridge K-2 type pH meter using suitable glass electrode. Five different sets were prepared for each ion present in the salt solution containing the total amount of the metal ion present corresponding to 10%, 25%, 50%, 75% and 125% of the symmetry concentration of the hydrogen present in the resin. The mixing in every case was carried out by placing the bottles in a constant temperature bath and they were allowed to remain there with occasional shaking for 7 days so that the equilibrium in all the cases might be attained.

After the period the bottles were taken out and the pH values of the solutions were measured directly in presence of the resin beads using the same pH meter. The resin beads were then separated from the liquid phase by a process of centrifugation-filtration using pyrex glass barrels provided with fritted discs. The separation of all the bottles of a particular set were carried out simultaneously. The process of centrifugation was carried out to constant weight and the weights of the different resin samples were taken. The amount of water present in the resin phase was calculated from this weight and the weight of the air dried resin giving due consideration to the change in weight owing to the exchange of the metal ion for hydrogen ion. The amount of metal present in solution was then estimated with standard EDTA solution using Murexide as indicator. From the total amount of the metal and the amount present in solution after exchange, the amount entered into the resin phase was calculated. The amount of hydrogen present inside the resin phase was calculated from this value and the exchange capacity of the resin. C_H^+ of the solution was known from the pH of the solution after exchange.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stability constants and the distribution constants of the exchange reaction between the hydrogen resin and $CuSO_4$ and $NiSO_4$ were calculated by using the molalities and the amounts of the ionic species in the resin phase and aqueous phase respectively. They are presented in Table 1 and 2 together with their percentage neutralisation at two different temperatures. The ΔF values of the reactions are obtained from the relations $-RT \ln k$ and $-RT \ln D$ and are given in the last two columns of the tables. The K values are calculated from the molal concentration of the ionic species and the distribution constant, D , is obtained from the distribution of ions in the resin and solution phases in equilibrium and is defined by the equation.

$$D = \frac{(\text{amount of metal ion in the resin phase}) \times (\text{amount of hydrogen ion})^2 \text{ in the solution phase}}{(\text{amount of metal ion in the solution phase}) \times (\text{amount of hydrogen ion})^2 \text{ in the resin phase}}$$

These two constants are of the same type, the only difference is that in one case the amount of water embedded in the resin phase and the total volume of the solution are considered. These constants are used to ascertain the role of water invasion inside the resin phase and the consequent swelling effect on the ease of complex formation.

The third column in the tables contains the amount of the salt added corresponding to the symmetry concentration of the resin as calculated from its exchange capacity. The molalities of the ions are given in the next four columns, the subscripts r and s are used

TABLE 1
 Exchange between H_2R and $CuSO_4$

No. of obs.	Temp. °C	Percentage of $CuSO_4$ added corresponding to symmetry concentration	$(Cu^{2+})_s$	$(H^+)_r$	$(Cu^{2+})_r$	$(H^+)_s$	Stability constant " K "	Distribution constant " D "	$-RT \ln K$ K.cals	$-RT \ln D$ K.cals
1	$10^\circ \pm 1$	25%	0.001742	11.96	2.073	0.0120	1.199×10^{-3}	1.059×10^2	+3.806	-2.638
2	"	50%	0.005184	9.426	2.014	0.01561	1.092×10^{-3}	0.8986 $\times 10^2$	+3.859	-2.545
3	"	75%	0.009956	11.53	1.813	0.02183	0.6530×10^{-3}	0.5618 $\times 10^2$	+4.150	-2.279
4	"	100%	0.0142	10.74	1.575	0.02450	0.5773×10^{-3}	0.5393 $\times 10^2$	+4.219	-2.256
5	"	125%	0.01934	9.253	1.069	0.03084	0.6144×10^{-3}	0.4402 $\times 10^2$	+4.183	-1.824
6	$35^\circ \pm 1$	25%	0.001508	12.09	2.605	0.01263	1.886×10^{-3}	1.634×10^2	+5.281	-2.138
7	"	50%	0.005429	10.90	3.185	0.01519	1.125×10^{-3}	0.9217 $\times 10^2$	+4.184	-2.785
8	"	75%	0.0101	12.04	2.804	0.02299	1.013×10^{-3}	0.8732 $\times 10^2$	+4.075	-2.752
9	"	100%	0.01728	11.62	1.878	0.02640	0.5610×10^{-3}	0.4673 $\times 10^2$	+4.610	-2.367
10	"	125%	0.02237	9.387	1.138	0.03174	0.582×10^{-3}	0.3914 $\times 10^2$	+4.587	-2.259

TABLE 2

 Exchange between H_2R and $NiSO_4$

No. of obs.	Temp. °C	Percentage of $NiSO_4$ added corresponding to symmetry concentration	$(Ni^{2+})_s$	$(H^+)_r$	$(Ni^{2+})_r$	$(H^+)_s$	Stability constant " K "	Distribution constant " D "	$-RT \ln K$ K.cals	$-RT \ln D$ K.cals
1	$10^\circ \pm 1$	25%	0.003430	7.732	0.4160	0.03013	1.842×10^{-3}	1.051×10^2	+3.563	-2.634
2	"	50%	0.007011	4.364	0.3576	0.02625	1.845×10^{-3}	0.6205 $\times 10^2$	+3.562	-2.336
3	"	75%	0.01150	4.334	0.5437	0.03014	0.288×10^{-3}	0.6937 $\times 10^2$	+3.440	-2.398
4	"	100%	0.01486	5.160	0.5310	0.02878	1.112×10^{-3}	0.4158 $\times 10^2$	+3.849	-2.109
5	"	125%	0.02058	9.026	0.9423	0.03793	0.8081×10^{-3}	0.5114 $\times 10^2$	+4.209	-2.226
6	$25^\circ \pm 1$	25%	0.006943	11.97	0.6366	0.01738	0.1932×10^{-3}	0.3599 $\times 10^2$	+5.100	-2.136
7	"	50%	0.006828	12.64	1.710	0.02090	0.6844×10^{-3}	0.5478 $\times 10^2$	+4.346	-2.386
8	"	75%	0.01113	9.234	3.207	0.01996	1.346×10^{-3}	0.7875 $\times 10^2$	+3.943	-2.604
9	"	100%	0.01144	7.812	1.384	0.02571	1.31×10^{-3}	0.6015 $\times 10^2$	+3.442	-2.443
10	"	125%	0.01695	8.2640	2.335	0.02513	1.354×10^{-3}	0.7297 $\times 10^2$	+3.939	-2.557

to denote the resin and solution phases respectively. The molality of the ions in the resin phase is calculated from the weight of the ions associated with the resin and the amount of water present inside the resin phase as obtained from the weight of the dry resin in the hydrogen form and the weight of the resin, water and the amount of the ion whose molality is to be calculated after centrifugation filtration of the resin to constant weight.

The formal ΔF values when calculated from the distribution constants of the ionic species involved in the reaction all show negative values in accordance with the normal spontaneous nature of the reactions. But when the amount of water present in the resin phase was considered, the values become positive which may be attributed to the swelling of the resin matrix thus making the reaction difficult. The variation of equilibrium and distribution constants with the percentage of salt added show similar pattern.

The values of the constants decrease as the percentage of salt added increases. In case of copper-complex the constants attain a more or less same value when the copper salt present is maximum. The change for those of Ni-complex are somewhat different. Usually they show an initial increase, reach a maximum value at 75% of Ni and then decrease. The D -values also show a further increase when the percentage of salt added is maximum. The concentrations of the ionic species are used, instead of their activities, in the calculation of the equilibrium constant which may be due to this variation as the percentage of exchange changes.

The thermodynamic constants like enthalpy changes and entropy changes of these reactions were also calculated by using the K - and D -values as obtained above. The enthalpy changes were evaluated from the slopes of the curves obtained by plotting $\log K$ or $\log D$ against $1/T$ and using the standard thermodynamic relations making use of the approximation that ΔH values are independent of temperature. Entropy changes were also calculated from these values and the corresponding free energy changes at different temperatures are given in Tables 3 and 4.

TABLE 3

Enthalpy and Entropy changes in the reaction between H_2R and $CuSO_4$

System	p.c. of $CuSO_4$ added corresponding to the symmetry concentration	ΔH_K cals	ΔH_D cals	Entropy change in E.U. (Cal-degree ⁻¹) at			
				10°		35°	
				ΔS_K	ΔS_D	ΔS_K	ΔS_D
1	25%	-3.87	3.50	-13.4	9.33	-17.1	6.95
2	75%	-3.50	3.69	-14.6	8.06	-13.2	8.94

The enthalpy and entropy change values are represented by the usual symbols ΔH and ΔS with subscripts K and D denoting that they are calculated from K - and D - values respectively. The entropy change values are all reasonably constant at a particular temperature and are independent of the percentage neutralisation. In case of copper complex only

two systems are utilised because in other cases the K - and D - values remain the same at different temperatures.

TABLE 4

Enthalpy and Entropy changes in the reaction between H_2R and $NiSO_4$

System	p.c. of $NiSO_4$ added corres- ponding to the symmetry concentration	ΔH_K Cal/s	ΔH_D Cal/s	Entropy change in E.U.(Cal-degree ⁻¹) at			
				10°		25°	
				ΔS_K	ΔS_D	ΔS_K	ΔS_D
1	25%	29.94	14.46	-12.4	9.35	-17.0	7.21
2	50%	14.76	1.75	-12.5	8.26	-14.5	8.01
3	75%	6.91	-1.38	-12.1	8.46	-13.2	8.73
4	100%	-1.98	-4.93	-13.6	7.43	-11.5	8.18
5	125%	-0.51	-5.11	-14.8	7.85	-13.2	8.56

In the case of copper-complex the enthalpy change seems to be independent of the percentage neutralized whereas it steadily decreases with the increasing amount of the salt-in the formation of Ni-complex. In most cases the calculated values are found to be reproducible within a limit of nearly 5-6% which is not large considering the slow attainment of equilibrium and the thermodynamic assumptions involved in the calculations.

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